

DIELECTROPHORETICALLY STRUCTURED PIEZOELECTRIC COMPOSITES

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1 General Introduction

Piezoelectric materials generally belong to either of two families: i) piezoelectric ceramics which exhibit high permittivity, thermal stability, piezo and pyroelectric effects and can be found in demanding applications. However, these materials are brittle and very difficult to shape. ii) piezoelectric polymers which have a modest sensitivity and a low thermal stability, but are rather flexible, and ductile and easy to process and are found in less demanding applications. Potentially, attractive combinations of mechanical, thermal, dielectric and electro-active properties and adequate processability can be achieved by embedding ferroelectric ceramic particles within a polymer matrix in which the ferroelectric activity is provided by the ceramic phase and the flexibility is provided by the polymer phase. Such composites can overcome the limitations of both ceramics and polymers and provide new avenues to sensing applications. One interesting application of such composites is in pyroelectric sensors. Pyroelectric materials generate a voltage upon a change of temperature. These materials find wide application in infrared (IR) detection owing to the advantages of wavelength-independent sensitivity and room temperature operation. These materials are normally characterized by the voltage responsivity or pyroelectric figure of merit (FOM) which is proportional to the pyroelectric coefficient, $p(T)$, and inversely proportional to the relative dielectric permittivity, ϵ .

$$\text{FOM} = p(T)/\epsilon$$

Eq. 1

Among various kinds of commercially available materials for IR detection applications lead titanate (PT) is regarded as a good pyroelectric material because of a very large spontaneous polarization of $81 \mu\text{C}/\text{cm}^2$, small relative dielectric constant, and a large pyroelectric coefficient. PT is a polycrystalline ferroelectric ceramic with a tetragonal perovskite structure at room temperature and a high Curie temperature of $490 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ [4,5]. Lead titanate ceramics have a high sensitivity but are brittle and demand high temperature sintering process. Therefore by embedding the pyroelectric ceramic particles within a polymer matrix in which the pyroelectric activity is provided by the ceramic phase and the flexibility is provided by the polymer phase it is possible to avoid the high temperature heat treatment and still achieve a combination of the best properties of each phase. There is also a possibility to tailor the dielectric permittivity of the composite material by altering the ceramic content. So the FOM can be optimized by combining the pyroelectric activity of the ceramic phase and dielectric constant of the composite. In such multiphase composites the pattern of connectivity of the two phases plays a crucial role as far as overall physical and electrical properties are concerned. Structuring the ceramic particles in PZT-polymer composites has shown to improve the piezoelectric properties of these materials over those of random composites by forming chains of aligned and (almost) connected particles when the matrix polymer is still in its low viscosity state [1-3]. This work firstly focuses on the use of dielectrophoresis (DEP) to optimise the structure and hence piezoelectric properties of the electroceramic-polymer composites and secondly

investigates the pyroelectric properties of such composites.

2 Theory

2.1 Random composites

The piezoelectric properties of PT-polymer composites are a function of the volume fraction of the constituent particles, the connectivity of the PT particles in three dimensions, aspect ratio of the particles and the piezoelectric properties of the particles. An appropriate analytical model to explain the dielectric properties of the random or 0-3 composites analyzed in this work is the model by Yamada et al. [6]. In these composites the ceramic constituents are randomly distributed in the polymer matrix. In Yamada's model the composite is assumed as a uniform distribution of ellipsoidal particles in an isotropic polymer matrix. The dielectric constant of the composite in the poling direction is given by:

$$\varepsilon_{random} = \varepsilon_m \left(1 + \frac{n\varphi(\varepsilon_c - \varepsilon_m)}{n\varepsilon_m + (\varepsilon_c - \varepsilon_m)(1 - \varphi)} \right) \quad \text{Eq. 2}$$

where ε_{random} is the dielectric constant of the 0-3 composite ε_m and ε_c are that of the polymer matrix and ceramic particles, respectively, φ is the volume fraction of the ceramic, and n is the inverse of the depolarization factor for an ellipsoidal particle in the direction of applied electric field. In the current work n was obtained for best fit of the experimental permittivity data to model predictions.

Yamada's model for piezoelectric charge constant in the poling direction of random composites is:

$$d_{33random} = \frac{\varphi \alpha n \varepsilon_{random} d_{33c}}{n \varepsilon_{random} + (\varepsilon_c - \varepsilon_m)} \quad \text{Eq. 3}$$

where α is the poling ratio of the ceramic particles and ε_{random} is the dielectric constant of the composite described previously.

2.2 Structured composites

An analytical model for the permittivity of structured composites is presented by Bowen et al. [3]. According to his model the composite is considered as a collection of particles aligned into chain-like structures along a specific direction separated by polymer gaps. The equation for the permittivity for such a composite is as follows:

$$\varepsilon_{structured} = \varphi \left(\frac{R\varepsilon_c\varepsilon_m}{\varepsilon_c + R\varepsilon_m} \right) + (1 - \varphi)\varepsilon_m \quad \text{Eq. 4}$$

where $\varepsilon_{structured}$ is the dielectric constant of dielectrophoretically structured 1-3 composites and R is the ratio of average particle size to the effective interparticle distance.

To describe the piezoelectric charge constant in structured composites the analytical model proposed by Van den Ende et al. [2] is applied. According to this model the d_{33} of composites are obtained by modelling the particle-matrix alternations in the chains as two capacitors in series in the electrical domain and two springs in series in the mechanical domain. The equation for d_{33} of 1-3 composite is given by:

$$d_{33structured} = \frac{(1+R)^2 \varepsilon_m \varphi Y_c d_{33c}}{\varepsilon_c + R\varepsilon_m [(1+R\varphi)Y_c + (1-\varphi)RY_m]} \quad \text{Eq. 5}$$

where Y_1 and Y_2 are elastic moduli of the polymer matrix and that of the ceramic in the direction of chains.

3 Experimental procedure

3.1 Composite manufacturing

The lead titanate (PT) powder used in this study was calcined at 800 °C for 2 h to develop single phase PbTiO_3 . The agglomerated powder was then dry-milled using 5-mm zirconium balls for 2 h using a single G90 jar mill. The particle size distribution of milled powder in an aqueous solution with 10% isopropyl alcohol measured by a Beckman Coulter LS230 laser diffraction analyzer was found to be $d(10)=2.42 \mu\text{m}$, $d(50)=4.53 \mu\text{m}$, and $d(90)=8.12 \mu\text{m}$. A two component epoxy system (Epotek 302-3M, Epoxy (diglycidyl ether of bisphenol-A (DGEBA) resin and poly(oxypropyl)-diamine (POPD) multifunctional aliphatic amine curing agent, was used. This epoxy is recommended for adhesive joining, sealing, and coating. It has excellent water, chemical and solvent resistance properties. The glass transition temperature (T_g) of the epoxy is 55 °C. It degrades at 350 °C, and can cure at any temperature between 20 to 200 °C. At room temperature the epoxy is viscous (at 800 - 1600 cPs) and has a dielectric constant (at 1 kHz) of approximately 3.4, which makes it an interesting

option for dielectrophoresis (DEP). To fabricate the composites the ceramic content was calculated using following equation:

$$M_C = M_P (\rho_C / \rho_P) (\varphi_C / (1 - \varphi_C)) \quad \text{Eq. 6}$$

here M is the mass, ρ is the density, and φ_C is the ceramic volume fraction. The subscript c and p show the ceramic and polymer properties, respectively. The PT particles were then dispersed in the resin component of the epoxy and mixed at the speed of 1000 rpm for 15 minutes using a planetary mixer (SpeedMixer DAC 150.1 FVZ, Hauschild). Subsequently, the hardener was added and the composite resin was again mixed at 1500 rpm for 3 minutes. Finally the uncured ceramic-polymer mixture was degassed and poured into a mold consisting of a 1 mm thick Teflon sheet with circular 15 mm diameter cut-outs, which was placed between two layers of 50 μm thick aluminium foil serving as the temporary electrodes for the application of the electric field for DEP as shown in Fig. 1. The whole set-up was placed between two bolted steel plates in presence of additional Teflon spacers separating the electrodes from the steel plates to apply pressure and produce flat samples. Structuring of the particles in the as-yet uncured composite was realised by a dielectrophoresis process in which an electric field of 2kV/mm and $f = 1200$ Hz was applied to the composite medium of particles dispersed in the uncured epoxy resin using a function generator (Agilent, 33210A) coupled to a high voltage amplifier (Radiant Technologies Inc., T6000HVA-2) at room temperature (RT) for 1h (i.e. well into the curing stage) followed by 5 h heating at 50 °C to get a fully cured matrix. The peak to peak output voltage of the high voltage amplifier, the phase angle and the leakage current were verified with an oscilloscope (Agilent, DSO-x 2004A). The experimental set-up is schematically shown in Fig. 2. The randomly dispersed samples were obtained without applying an electric field by oven curing at 50 °C for 5 hours. The completely cured disk-shaped samples of 15mm diameter and 1mm thickness were polished to remove the top epoxy layer and post cured at 100 °C for 1 hour to remove moisture. Finally, gold electrodes of 10mm diameter, 50nm thickness were deposited on both sides of the composite samples by sputtering (Balzers Union, SCD 040) and poled at 7 kV/mm at

100 °C in a water-cooled Julabo, SE Class III, 12876 oil bath for a 1 hour.

Fig. 1. Schematic drawing of the mold used for processing the (dielectrophoretically structured) composites.

Fig. 2. Schematic diagram of DEP setup in a safety box.

The samples were then cooled to RT in presence of the poling field and stored at 50 °C for 24 hours with their electrodes short circuited prior to the measurements in order to remove the injected charges during the polarization and the trapped charges due to impurities. Thermal expansion measurements were conducted with a computer controlled PerkinElmer Diamond Thermomechanical Analyzer (TMA). The samples were positioned inside a thermal chamber heated at 5 °C/min. The probe displacement and the

temperature were recorded and the linear thermal expansion coefficients were calculated.

3.2 Electrical measurements

The dielectric constant of the composites were measured using the parallel plate capacitor method with an Agilent 4263B LCR meter (Japan) at 1 V and 1 kHz. d_{33} measurements were performed with a Berlincourt type M3001 d_{33} meter, KCF technologies (State College, PA).

The pyroelectric constant of the materials was determined from the change in total charge at the electrodes due to a change in sample temperature using the direct method [7]. The poled sample was placed in Agilent 16339A component test fixture with its electrodes connected to the measurement device as shown in Fig. 3 and heated uniformly using an integrated resistor as a programmable heater. The heating cycle was from room temperature to 70 °C, lower than the poling temperature. The heating rate was controlled by a PID controller and kept constant at 5 °C/min during the measurement.

Fig. 3. Schematic view of the device under test placed inside the shielding box in the direct measurement method.

The depolarization current flowing between the two contacts of the sample was monitored with Agilent 4339B high resistance meter and stored as shown in Fig. 4. The temperature monitored with a k-type thermocouple and also stored in the computer. The heating cycle normally started from room temperature. The whole process was controlled by a labview program while the operator determined the heating rate and the maximum test temperature. So the pyroelectric coefficient was calculated as:

$$p(T) = I_p A (dT/dt) \quad \text{Eq. 7}$$

where I_p is the measured pyroelectric current, and dT/dt is the constant heating rate which was chosen as 5 °C/min over the whole temperature range. The measurement of I_p gives a direct plot of $p(T)$ over the range of the temperature.

Fig. 4. Schematic diagram of the set-up for the direct pyroelectric current measurement.

The microstructures of the samples were observed using a field emission-scanning electron microscope (FE-SEM) (JEOL, JSM-7500F) operated in backscattered electron mode. Samples sectioned parallel to the formed particle chains were embedded into a room temperature curing epoxy and polished with 1 μm diamond paste.

4 Results and discussion

4.1 Microstructure of composites

The effect of DEP structuring on the SEM microstructures of the composite samples is shown in Fig. 5. A clear difference can be observed between random and structured samples in particular for 10-20 % PT composites. It is clearly visible that during dielectrophoresis, ceramic particles orient themselves and form short chain like structures of particles along the electric field direction.

Fig. 5. SEM micrographs of random (labelled R) and structured (labelled S) PT-epoxy composites with PT volume fractions of 10% (a), 20% (b) and 30% (c).

4.2 Piezoelectric properties

In Fig. 6, the permittivity results are presented for PT volume fractions from 10% to 50%. The experimental data for random composites are fitted to Yamada's model (Eq. 2).

Fig. 6. Measured permittivity values for structured and random composites with their associated analytical model.

The properties of the structured composites are fitted to Bowen's model (Eq. 4). The values that were measured for the dielectrophoretically structured samples are higher than those for random composites for the complete range of PT volume fractions. During the dielectrophoresis process, PT particles are redistributed to form chains in the

electric field direction, and hence, the properties are also enhanced in that direction.

The influence of DEP structuring on d_{33} values of the composites is shown in Fig. 7. The experimentally observed d_{33} values of both structured and random composites were compared with Yamada's model (Eq. 3) and the model proposed by van den Ende et al. (Eq. 5). Clearly ordering of the PT ceramic particles in PT-epoxy composites has resulted in improved piezoelectric charge constant of these materials.

Fig. 7. The d_{33} values for structured and random composites with their associated analytical model.

The piezoelectric voltage coefficient, g_{33} , can be calculated by dividing the d_{33} of the composite by its permittivity. The variation of g_{33} of the composites as a function of PT volume fraction presented in Fig. 8. The maximum value obtained for the random composites is 48 mVm/N at PT volume fraction of 30%, while for the structured composite, a value of 73 mVm/N is reached at PT volume fraction of 20%. For the structured composites the d_{33} increment is higher than that of dielectric constant especially at lower volume fractions. Therefore, the voltage coefficient of these composites exhibits a maximum at low volume fraction of PT. At higher volume fractions than 20%, the improvement in g_{33} properties of structured composites decreases rapidly.

Fig. 8. The g_{33} values for structured and random composites with their associated analytical model.

In the models proposed by Bowen (Eq. 4) and Van den Ende (Eq. 5) the ratio, R , of interparticle distance over the particle size in the direction of the electric field is an important parameter influencing the fraction of the applied electric field acting on the ceramic particles. The interparticle distances estimated by fitting the models to the experimental data obtained for ϵ and d_{33} for the structured composites and calculated from the SEM micrographs for the random composites are presented in Fig. 9.

Fig. 9. Estimated values of the average interparticle distance, obtained by fitting model predictions to the measured data for structured composites and calculated from SEM microstructures for random composites.

The average interparticle distances in a random composite decreases with increasing PT volume fraction, meaning that the particles become more closely packed in every direction. The estimated interparticle distance for the dielectrophoretically structured composites from Bowen model (Eq. 4) and Van den Ende model (Eq. 5) are $0.28 \mu\text{m}$ and $0.32 \mu\text{m}$ respectively. So Van den Ende model predicts slightly higher interparticle distance for the structured composites than the Bowen model.

4.3 Pyroelectric properties

Fig. 10 shows the behaviour of the pyroelectric coefficient $p(T)$ of random composites as a function of temperature in the range of $30 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ to $70 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. As the pyroelectric activity is due to the electro-active ceramic phase, with increasing the ceramic volume content a higher pyroelectric coefficient is exhibited. It should be also noted that the probability of existing continuous ceramic paths between the upper and lower electrodes increases with increasing PT content. So the combination of these two effects enhances the pyroelectric activity of the composites with higher PT volume content. At $30 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ the pyroelectric coefficient increases by 30% when the ceramic volume fraction rises from 10% to 50%. In the measured temperature range for all tested composites a local minima can be observed very close to the glass transition temperature (T_g) of the polymer phase ($55 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$). This behaviour can be explained by the results of the linear thermal expansion coefficients of the composites in the range of $30 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ to $70 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. All random composites of PT volume fractions from 10% to 50% showed expansion upon heating from room temperature up to the glass transition temperature, after which they experienced shrinkage up to $70 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. Therefore it can be stated that during expansion the ceramic particles get pulled apart and electron transport becomes more difficult within the insulating polymer matrix, so the pyroelectric coefficient decreases. Passing through the glass transition temperature range the polymer phase becomes more rubbery and particles can relax within the new polymer state. So the resulting pyroelectric coefficient increase as a function of temperature. This shows a high dependence of pyroelectric properties on temperature as also reported by Bhalla et al. [8].

Moreover the electrical resistivity measurement of pure epoxy as a function of temperature shows that the electrical resistivity of this material possess almost a constant value (1.2×10^{12} ohm.cm) up to the glass transition temperature, above which it starts to decrease (55 °C) and at 70 °C it shows resistivity of 2×10^{11} ohm.cm. This behaviour is in agreement with the so-called Arrhenius behaviour of the electrical conductivity as a function of reciprocal temperature for polymers [9].

Fig. 10. The measured pyroelectric coefficients for random composites of 10% to 50% PT as a function of temperature.

The pyroelectric FOMs of the random composites at 30 °C are plotted versus different PT volume fractions from 10% to 50% in Fig. 11. With increasing the electro-active ceramic content the FOM of the composite increases. The same trend has been observed by Yamazaki et al. [10] for PT-PVDF composites. So unlike the piezoelectric properties that maximum g_{33} was obtained for a low PT volume fraction, the pyroelectric responsivity increases with ceramic loading over the whole volume range from 10% to 50% PT.

Table 1 compares the values of pyroelectric FOM of some example ceramics and composites with that of 50%PT-epoxy composite obtained in the current work. It can be seen that the highest pyroelectric FOM value obtained for the random 50%PT-epoxy composite is comparable to the FOM of PZT ceramics. However it is still much lower than the pyroelectric FOM of pure PT which is $3 \mu\text{C}/\text{m}^2 \text{ } ^\circ\text{C}$. The reason could be associated with the very high

Curie temperature of PT ceramics (490 °C) which makes them difficult to pole. Furthermore the poling efficiency is very low due to the large difference in dielectric properties of the polymer matrix and the ceramic particles.

Fig. 11. Pyroelectric FOM for random PT-epoxy composites as a function of PT content.

Material	FOM ($\mu\text{C}/\text{m}^2 \text{ } ^\circ\text{C}$)	Test Temperature ($^\circ\text{C}$)	Ref.
PT	3	RT	11
PZT	0.25	RT	12
50%PZT-PVDF	0.11	30	12
50%PT-PVDF	2.2	RT	10
50%PT-epoxy	0.24	30	

Table1. FOM of some selected materials.

For a 0-3 composite consisting of spherical ceramic grains embedded in a matrix, the electric field acting on an isolated spherical grain E_1 is given by [13]:

$$E_1 = E_0 \frac{3 \varepsilon_m}{\varepsilon_c + 3\varepsilon_m} \quad \text{Eq. 8}$$

In this equation, ε_m and ε_c are the dielectric constants of the spherical ferroelectric grains and polymer matrix, respectively, and E_0 is the externally applied electric field. Since the epoxy matrix has a lower dielectric constant (4.6) compared to PT ceramics (200), during poling most of the applied electric field is concentrated in the polymer and about 6% of the applied electric field acts on the ceramic particles which leads to the low efficiency of the poling process. In order to

sufficiently polarize the ceramic particles the electric field acting on them has to be in the range of coercive field of the ferroelectric ceramic particles which is 6 kV/mm for PT [14]. According to analytical models developed by Wong and Shin [15] the electrical conductivity of the polymer matrix plays a very important role in defining the piezoelectric and pyroelectric properties of the composites. A high conductivity matrix alters the internal fields in the composites and allows accumulation and dissipation of free charge on the particle-matrix interface which can enhance the permittivity, pyroelectric and piezoelectric coefficients of the composites.

5 Conclusions

Significant improvement in piezoelectric properties of PT-epoxy composites can be achieved by dielectrophoretic alignment of the ceramic particles inside the polymer matrix, especially at low volume fractions of PT, which favours higher flexibility and a lower density of the composites. The pyroelectric behaviour of 0-3 composites reveal an improvement in pyroelectric FOM for higher volume fraction composites. Using a polymer matrix with higher electrical conductivity and higher permittivity will enhance the poling efficiency and the final pyroelectric and piezoelectric coefficients of the composites.

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References

- [1]. S. A. Wilson, G. M. Maistros and R. W. Whatmore "Structure modification of 0–3 piezoelectric ceramic/polymer composites through dielectrophoresis" *J. Phys. D: Appl. Phys.* vol. 38, pp. 175, 2005.
- [2]. D. A. van den Ende, B. F. Bory, W. A. Groen, and S. van der Zwaag "Improving the d_{33} and g_{33} properties of 0-3 piezoelectric composites by Dielectrophoresis" , *J. Appl. Phys.* pp. 107, 2010.
- [3]. C.P. Bowen, R.E. Newnham and C.A. Randall "Dielectric properties of dielectrophoretically assembled particulate-polymer composites" *J. Mater. Res.*, vol. 13, no. 1, pp. 205, 1998.
- [4]. C.M. Wang, Y.C. Chen, Y. T. Huang, M.C. Kao, "Calcium modified lead titanate thin films for pyroelectric applications", *Applications of Ferroelectrics*, 2000. ISAF, vol.2, pp. 771, 2000.
- [5]. M. Srinivasan, "Pyroelectric materials," *Bulletin of Materials Science*, vol. 6, pp. 317, 1984.
- [6]. T. Yamada, T. Ueda, and T. Kitayama, "Piezoelectricity of a high-content lead zirconate titanate/polymer composite" *J. Appl. Phys.*, vol. 53, no. 6, pp. 4328, 1982.
- [7]. R. Byer and C. Roundy, "Pyroelectric coefficient direct measurement technique and application to a Nsec response time detector," *IEEE Transactions on Sonics and Ultrasonics*, vol. 19, pp. 333, 1972.
- [8]. A. S. Bhalla, R. E. Newnham, L. E. Cross, W. A. Schulze, J. P. Dougherty, W. A. Smith, "Pyroelectric PZT-polymer composites", *Ferroelectrics*, vol. 33, iss. 1, pp. 139, 1981.
- [9]. R. Dewsberry, "The electrical conductivity and its relationship to the glass transition temperature of plasticized polyacrylonitrile", *J. Phys. D: Appl. Phys.* vol. 9, no. 14, pp. 2049, 1976.
- [10]. H. Yamazaki, T. Kitayama, "Pyroelectric properties of polymer-ferroelectric composites" *Ferroelectrics*, vol. 33, iss. 1, pp. 147, 1981.
- [11]. C. J. Dias, D. K. Das-Gupta, "Inorganic ceramic/polymer ferroelectric composite electrets", *IEEE Transactions on Dielectrics and Electrical Insulation*, vol. 3, no. 5, pp. 706, 1996.
- [12]. G. P. Estevam, W. L. Barros de Melo, and W. K. Sakamoto, "Photopyroelectric response of PTCa/PEEK composite" *Rev. Sci. Instrum*, vol. 82, pp. 023903, 2011.
- [13]. A. R. von Hippel, "Dielectrics and Waves", Wiley, New York, 1954.
- [14]. Y. Xu, "Ferroelectric Materials and Their Applications", North Holland, 1991.
- [15]. C.K. Wong and F.G. Shin, "Effect of electrical conductivity on poling and the dielectric, pyroelectric and piezoelectric properties of ferroelectric 0-3 composites", *J. Mater. Sci.*, vol. 41, no. 1, pp. 229, 2006.